

TABLE 1 - INTERACTION OF TETRA-O-ACETYL-D-GLUCOPYRANOSYL BROMIDE (0.04 M) AND ARYL THIOCARBAMIDE (0.04 M) IN ISOPROPANOL

Sl. No.	Aryl thiocarbamide (g)	S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide m. p. °C yield (g)	Analysis %		$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ in CHCl ₃	λ_{max} (nm)	$\log \epsilon_{max}$	m. p. °C	Picrate Analysis %	
			Found	Calcd.					Found	Calcd.
1.	-Phenyl (6.0)	-Phenyl (IIIa) 138, (5.0)	N, 5.58 S, 6.54	N, 5.80 S, 6.39	+5.86° (c 2.2134)	244	(4.9354)	155	N, 9.51 S, 5.0	N, 9.84 S, 4.51
2.	-o-Tolyl (6.6)	-o-Tolyl (IIb) 135, (6.0)	N, 5.55 S, 6.28	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	-3.39° (c 2.359)	245	(4.0228)	145	N, 9.29 S, 5.23	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
3.	-m-Tolyl (6.6)	-m-Tolyl (IIIc) 133, (5.5)	N, 5.26 S, 6.95	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	+8.16° (c 1.975)	245	(4.5588)	129	N, 9.58 S, 4.74	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
4.	-p-Tolyl (6.6)	-p-Tolyl (IIId) 123, (2.0)	N, 5.58 S, 6.79	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	+1.82° (c 3.3796)	245.5	(3.8858)	152	N, 9.19 S, 3.65	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
5.	-o-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-o-Cl-Phenyl (IIIe) 136, (3.5)	N, 5.30 S, 6.13	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	-13.58° (c 4.4266)	243.5	(4.9434)	147	N, 7.98 S, 3.84	N, 9.39 S, 4.29
6.	-m-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-m-Cl-Phenyl (III f) 151, (3.0)	N, 5.50 S, 6.34	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	+4.55° (c 3.057)	243.5	(4.972)	141	N, 8.06 S, 5.77	N, 9.39 S, 4.29
7.	-p-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-p-Cl-Phenyl (III g) 128, (2.4)	N, 5.50 S, 6.87	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	+1.59° (c 4.0288)	243.5	(4.8948)	135	N, 8.35 S, 4.62	N, 9.39 S, 4.29

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all compounds.

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On Glucosyl Thioureides. Part II. Preparation of 2-S-tetra-O-Acetyl-D-Glucopyranosyl-1,5-Disubstituted-2,4-Isodithiobiurets and 1,5-Disubstituted-2-Isothiobiurets

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RECENTLY, we reported a method for preparation of several S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides by the interaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide and aryl thiocarbamides^{1,2}. It was considered interesting to study the chemistry of these glucosyl aryl isothiocarbamides with special reference to their reaction with aryl isothiocya-

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nate and aryl isocyanates. The findings are presented in this note.

Reaction of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide and phenyl isothiocyanate in boiling acetone medium gives a clear solution. On mixing the acetone solution with petroleum ether, an oily liquid separates which on triturations several times with petroleum ether gives a granular solid, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 122°. The product is desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition the smell of phenylisothiocyanate is perceptible. The product has specific rotation², $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +4.96 (chloroform, c 3.5384) and λ_{max} 246 nm ($\log \epsilon_{max}$ 5.0799)⁴. The ir spectrum of the product indicates the presence of ν_{NH} (3310 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{C=O}$ (1740 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{C=N}$ (1600 cm^{-1}) $\nu_{C=S}$ (1040 cm^{-1}) and ν_{C-S} (750 cm^{-1}) bands^{4,5}. The product with m.p. 122° has therefore, been assigned the structure 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia).

The other S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides² also on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate under identical conditions afford the related 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1-aryl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib-Ig) (Table 1).

Similarly, the reaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide and phenyl isocyanate in cold benzene medium affords a product, crystallized from ethanol m.p. 159°. This has been assigned the structure 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2-isothiobiuret (IIa) on the basis of following facts:

The product is non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition

TABLE 1—INTERACTION OF S-TETRA-O-ACETYL-D-GLUCOPYRANOSYL ARYL ISOTHIOCARBAMIDES (0.01 M) AND PHENYL ISOTHIOCYANATE (0.01 M). SOLVENT : ACETONE

Sl. No.	S-Tetra-O-acetyl D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide (g)	2-S-Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I) m.p. (°C), yield (g)	Analysis %		[α] _D ²⁵ in chloroform (c)	Picrate m.p. (°C)	Analysis %		λ _{max} (nm)	log ε _{max}
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.		
1.	-Phenyl, 4.8	-1-5-Diphenyl (Ia), 122, 4.0	C : 54.18 H : 5.13 N : 6.97 S : 9.29	C : 54.45 H : 5.02 N : 6.80 S : 10.37	+ 4.96 (3.5384)	85 (d)	N : 9.35 N : 9.92	246.0	5.0799	
2.	-o-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-o-tolyl (Ib), 120, 4.5	N : 6.10 S : 9.80	N : 6.65 S : 10.14	-42.13 (3.0008)	86 (d)	N : 8.94 N : 9.76	245.0	3.7410	
3.	-m-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-m-tolyl (Ic), 104, 3.5	N : 6.04 S : 9.52	N : 6.65 S : 10.14	-28.68 (3.4860)	91 (d)	N : 8.89 N : 9.76	248.5	4.3176	
4.	-p-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-p-tolyl (Id), 95 (d), 3.8	N : 5.90 S : 9.18	N : 6.65 S : 10.14	-69.52 (5.3280)	102 (d)	N : 8.87 N : 9.76	245.0	4.5972	
5.	o-Cl-Phenyl, 5.1	1-o-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (Ie) 132, 4.2	N : 5.82 S : 9.15	N : 6.44 S : 9.82	-21.62 (2.6944)	120 (d)	N : 8.90 N : 9.54	246.5	4.7094	
6.	m-Cl-Phenyl, 5.1	1-m-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (If), 130, 3.0	N : 5.63 S : 9.09	N : 6.44 S : 9.82	-2.04 (3.1432)	78 (d)	N : 9.03 N : 9.54	246.5	5.3043	
7.	p-Cl-Phenyl, 5.1	1-p-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (Ig), 87(d), 3.2	N : 6.00 S : 8.95	N : 6.44 S : 9.82	-37.08 (3.1164)	108 (d)	N : 9.99 N : 9.54	244.0	4.4673	

TABLE 2—INTERACTION OF S-TETRA-O-ACETYL-D-GLUCOPYRANOSYL ARYL ISOTHIOCARBAMIDES (0.01 M) AND PHENYL ISOCYANATE (0.01 M). SOLVENT : BENZENE.

Sl. No.	S-Tetra-O-acetyl D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide (g)	2-S-Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2-isothiobiurets (II) m p. (°C), Yield (g)	Analysis %		[α] _D ²⁵ in chloroform (c)	λ _{max} (nm)	log ε _{max}
			Found	Calcd.			
1.	-Phenyl, 4.8	-1,5-Diphenyl (IIa), 159, 4.0	C : 55.72 H : 4.95 N : 6.51 S : 5.67	C : 55.90 H : 5.16 N : 6.98 S : 5.32	-5.0 (3.9492)	255.5	4.3107
2.	-o-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-o-tolyl (IIb), 151, 4.5	N : 6.39 S : 4.93	N : 6.82 S : 5.20	-7.58 (3.7420)	256.5	3.9609
3.	-m-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-m-tolyl (IIc), 158, 5.0	N : 6.58 S : 4.26	N : 6.82 S : 5.20	-1.78 (2.2164)	256.0	3.7533
4.	-p-Tolyl, 4.9	-5-Phenyl-1-p-tolyl (IId), 155, 3.0	N : 6.34 S : 5.72	N : 6.82 S : 5.20	-2.68 (2.2092)	256.5	4.3263
5.	o-Cl-Phenyl-5.1	-1-o-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (IIe), 161, 3.2	N : 6.50 S : 5.43	N : 6.60 S : 5.03	-37.57 (3.7996)	256.0	4.0313
6.	m-Cl-Phenyl, 5.1	-1-m-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (IIf), 154, 3.7	N : 6.75 S : 5.03	N : 6.60 S : 5.03	-15.11 (3.4136)	256.5	5.0502
7.	p-Cl-Phenyl, 5.1	-1-p-Cl-Phenyl-5-phenyl (IIg), 163, 4.2	N : 6.24 S : 4.84	N : 6.60 S : 5.03	-8.69 (4.0884)	256.0	4.7721

the odour of phenylisocyanate is perceptible. The product has [α]_D²⁵ -5.0 (chloroform, c 3.9492) and λ_{max} 255.5 nm (log ε_{max} 4.3107). The ir spectrum of the product clearly indicates the presence of ν_{NH} (3310 cm⁻¹), ν_{C=O} (1740 cm⁻¹), ν_{C=N} (1610 cm⁻¹) and ν_{C-S} (740 cm⁻¹) bands.

When the reaction of phenyl isocyanate is extended to other S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides the related 2-isothiobiurets (IIb-IIg) are isolated (Table 2).

Experimental

The required S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides are prepared as described earlier³. The phenyl isothiocyanate is prepared by the oxidation of ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate with lead nitrate. The phenyl isocyanate used is of commercial grade.

I. Preparation of 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I) : Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows:

The phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 M, 1.2 ml) is added to an acetone solution of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide (0.01 M, 4.82 g in 30 ml) and the mixture is refluxed on water bath for 8 hr. It is cooled and petroleum ether (10 ml) is added when an oily liquid separates out. The oily liquid is triturated several times with petroleum ether, when a

pale yellow solid (Ia) is formed (4 g), crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 122° (Found : C,54.18 ; H,5.13 ; N,6.97 ; S,9.29. $C_{28}H_{31}O_9N_3S_2$ requires : C,54.45 ; H,5.02 ; N, 6.80 ; S, 10.37%).

The other 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1, 5-diaryl-2, 4-isodithiobiurets are prepared by the interaction of phenylisothiocyanate and corresponding 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (Table 1).

II. *Preparation of 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2-isothiobiurets (II)* : Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows : The phenyl isocyanate (0.01M, 1.3 ml) is added to a benzene solution of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide (0.01M, 4.82g in 30 ml). The mixture is kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. On mixing with petroleum ether it affords a granular solid (4 g), crystallized from ethanol, m. p. 159° (Found : C,55.72 ; H,4.95 ; N,6.51 ; S,5.67. $C_{28}H_{31}O_{10}N_3S$ requires : C,55.90 ; H,5.16 ; N,6.98 ; S,5.32%).

The other-2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2-isothiobiurets are prepared by the interaction of phenyl isocyanate and related S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (Table 2).

The $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ of all the products are recorded in chloroform on Bellingham Polarimeter using sodium D-line. The uv spectra are recorded on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and the samples are prepared in chloroform. The ir spectra are recorded on Carl-Zeiss, Specord-75, spectrophotometer and the samples are prepared in Nujol as mull.

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Synthesis of Thiazolo-thienopyrimidines

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SYNTHESIS of novel heterocyclics from 2-amino-3-carbomethoxy-4,5-dimethylthiophene (I) was reported by us in previous publications^{1,2}. We report now the synthesis of some thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidines from it.

Condensation of I with α -thiocyanoacetophenone (IIa) furnished 2,3-dimethyl-8-phenyl-4H-thiazolo [3,2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidine-4-one (IIIa), the reaction having taken place as shown in the Chart I given below. The other derivatives of α -thiocyanoacetophenone (IIb-e) similarly condensed with I to give III b-e respectively.

Chart I

a, Ar = C_6H_5 ; b, Ar = $p\text{-Cl.C}_6H_4^-$; c, Ar = $p\text{-Br.C}_6H_4^-$; d, Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3.C_6H_4^-$; e, Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3O.C_6H_4^-$

PMR* spectrum of IIIa which gave signals at 2.48 (3H, s, CH_3 at C-3), 2.66(3H, s, CH_3 at C-2), 7.3-7.8 (6H, m, C_6H_5 and vinyl proton) confirms the structure but does not rule out the possibility for the compound to have linear structure VI. The isomeric compound VI was therefore synthesised in an unambiguous way. It was found to be a compound different from III as shown by m.p., tlc, etc. The compound VI was synthesised by condensing I with 2-chloro-4-phenylthiazole (IV) the reaction taking place as shown in Chart II below.

Chart II

The compound III and VI were reported earlier by Sauter *et al*³ who obtained them by treating 5, 6-dime-

*Chemical shifts given in this paper are in δ (ppm.)